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Review Article

**A REVIEW: PLANT-DERIVED NATURAL
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Department of Pharmaceutics, Bapatla College of Pharmacy, Bapatla – 522101, India.**Abstract: -**

*The concept of immunomodulation, introduced by Edward Jenner in 1796, has revolutionized the treatment of autoimmune diseases, viral infections, and certain cancers. Conditions like rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory bowel diseases, and systemic lupus erythematosus are characterized by abnormal immune responses, involving cytokines like tumor necrosis factor- α and interleukins. Immunomodulation, which modifies immune responsiveness, has led to the exploration of phytochemicals as immunostimulants or immunosuppressants. For centuries, medicinal plants have been used to alter immune systems, and recent studies have confirmed their immunomodulatory potential. This review highlights 58 plants, including *Curcuma longa*, *Andrographis paniculata*, Resveratrol, *Moringa oleifera* and *Tinospora cordifolia*, whose phytochemicals flavonoids, terpenoids, polysaccharides, and alkaloids exhibit immunomodulating properties. By integrating phytochemical, pharmacological, and therapeutic aspects, this article provides an up-to-date understanding of medicinal plants as immunomodulators, offering insights into their mechanisms of action and potential applications.*

Keywords: Immunomodulators, Immunostimulants, Immunosuppressants, Traditional plants

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INTRODUCTION:

Nowadays, In the 21st century, the world health sector is facing different problems. Among the problems faced by the scientific communities are antibiotic resistance antiviral resistance, and anticancer resistance [1], side effects of commercial drugs, undeveloped drug delivery mechanism, treatment of cardiovascular disease, metabolic disorder, COVID-19, inflammation, and neurological disorder [2]. The scientific community forecasts that due to only antibacterial resistance, by 2050, ten million people's death is expected [3]. Twenty-two million people's death is also expected by 2030 due to cardiovascular disease [4].

For centuries, plants and natural products have been utilized to promote well-being and health. Ancient Indian scriptures, particularly the Vedic literature, extensively document the medicinal properties of various plants. Specifically, the Rig Veda mentions 67 plants, the Sama Veda 81, the Yajur Veda 81, the Atharva Veda 289, the Brahmana 129, and the Upanishads 31. Ayurvedic therapeutics places significant emphasis on disease prevention, encapsulated in the concept of 'Vyadhirodhak Chamataav,' which refers to the body's innate capacity to resist disease [5]

A significant portion of India's population relies on plants and natural products for their preventive, curative, healing and therapeutic properties, as well as their immune-boosting effects [6]. These natural remedies are preferred over synthetic immunostimulants like levamisole and thalidomide, which can have severe side effects including nephrotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, bone marrow depression and gastrointestinal disturbances. Plant-based immunomodulators offer a safer, more effective and affordable alternative [7].

Immune System: -

The human system is a complex network of cells, tissues, molecules and a natural defense system against various infectious diseases, harmful pathogens and foreign invaders. This immune system is triggered by various factors, including small doses of antigens, infections, and external stimuli [8]. Center to the defense mechanism white blood cells (WBCs) and immune molecules, which play a vital role in responding to potential threats. Upon recognizing a foreign particle or pathogen, a coordinated and collective response is initiated, involving specific cells and mediators working together to eliminate the threat, a process known as the immune response [9].

Disorders of human immunity: -

The human immune system is a complex and highly efficient entity, characterized by its specificity, adaptability, and inducibility. Despite its remarkable capabilities, the immune system can fail, leading to various immunological disorders. These failures can be categorized into three primary groups: immunodeficiencies, where the immune response is inadequate; autoimmunity, where the immune system targets self-components; and hypersensitivities, where the immune response is excessive or inappropriate [10].

Immunodeficiencies: -

Immunodeficiency disorders result from impaired immune system function. Malnutrition, especially protein deficiency, is a significant contributor in developing countries, affecting cell-mediated immunity, complement activity, and cytokine production. Specific nutrient deficiencies, including zinc, iron, and vitamins A, C, E, B6, and B9, also weaken immune responses. These deficiencies can be inherited or acquired through various factors [10].

Autoimmunity: -

Autoimmune diseases occur when the immune system mistakenly targets self-tissues and cells, failing to differentiate between them and foreign antigens. This immune system malfunction triggers a destructive response, leading to conditions such as rheumatoid arthritis, systemic lupus erythematosus, multiple sclerosis, and Type 1 diabetes [11].

Hypersensitivity: -

Hypersensitivity is categorized into antibody-mediated and cell-mediated responses. The former includes Types I-III, while the latter encompasses Type IV. This immunological response occurs in two phases: sensitization, where the immune system initially recognizes the antigen, and the effectors phase, where immunologic memory triggers tissue damage upon subsequent antigen exposure [12].

The immune system operates through two primary mechanisms: innate immunity and adaptive immunity.

Innate immunity: -

The innate immune system constitutes the body's initial defense mechanism against harmful pathogens. It comprises multiple layers of protection, including physical barriers (such as skin, hair and mucus), chemical defenses (like salt in skin and tears in eyes) and blood proteins. Additionally, various immune cells play crucial roles, including phagocytic cells (macrophages and dendritic cells), mast cells, neutrophils, basophils, eosinophils and natural killer cells (NK, NKT and gd T cells). Upon encountering pathogens, these innate immune cells and other cells

release cytokines, signaling molecules that trigger the adaptive immune response. [13]

Adaptive immunity: - The adaptive immune response employs two key mechanisms: humoral & cellular immunity. Humoral immunity is mediated by B cells that recognize antigens through B-cell receptors or secreted antibodies, binding directly to serum antigens. In contrast, cellular immunity involves T lymphocytes recognizing peptide fragments presented by major

histocompatibility complex (MHC) molecules on cell surfaces, triggering cell lysis and cytokine release. T cells are categorized into subsets based on surface protein expression and function: cytotoxic T cells (CD8+), helper T cells (CD4+) and regulatory T cells. Cytotoxic T cells eliminate infected or cancerous cells, while helper T cells activate B and T lymphocytes by secreting cytokines and recognizing exogenous antigens complexed with MHC II [14].

Immunomodulators: -

Immunomodulators are substances, whether naturally occurring or synthetically produced, that have the ability to influence and regulate the immune system's functioning. These agents can either stimulate or suppress various components of the immune response, encompassing both the innate and adaptive immune systems. By modulating the immune system's activity, immunomodulators can restore balance to pathological processes, thereby normalizing immune function and promoting overall well-being [15].

Immunomodulators are categorized into three broad classes:

Immunosuppressants: - Immunosuppressants are substances that suppress immune responses, preventing excessive immunity. By inhibiting specific components of the immune system, these agents will effectively treat and manage auto-immune disorders like rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory bowel disease & graft-versus-host disease. Immunosuppressants also

facilitate organ transplantation by reducing rejection risk [16].

Immunostimulants: - Immunostimulants, including interferons and recombinant interleukin-2, amplify immune responses to the diseases like cancer. These therapeutic agents enhance the body's natural defense mechanisms, bolstering its ability to fight cancer cells & other antigens. Specifically, interferons stimulate immune cells, while interleukin-2 boosts T-cell and natural killer cell activity. This enhanced immunity helps in the conditions such as graft-versus-host disease [17].

Immunoadjuvants: - Immunoadjuvants are specialized chemicals paired with antigens to intensify immune responses. By stabilizing antigens, they boost vaccine effectiveness, amplifying the body's defensive reactions. These immune stimulants enhance vaccine potency, ensuring optimal protection against pathogens.[18].

Table: - 1 Immunosuppressants plant derived bioactive, microbe-derived drugs

S.NO	DRUG	USES	MECHANISM OF ACTION	REF
1	Cortisone	Used to treat rheumatoid arthritis disease	By suppressing the leukocyte migration to the site of inflammation	19
2	Leflunomide	Antirejection	It inhibits T and B cell proliferations	19,20
3	Cyclophosphamide	Treat malignancies	Inhibit T & B cell proliferations	21
4	Plant-derived bioactive Resveratrol, epigallocatechin-3gallate	Anti-inflammatory, anticancer	By blocking the NF-KB in LPS & PMA & blocking COX-2	22
5	Andrographolide	To Treat cancer	It prevents tumor cell growth by the anti-inflammatory effect	22
6	<i>Microbe-derived drug</i> Sirolimus	Antirejection	Prohibits T- lymphocyte activation & proliferation	20
7	Mycophenolate mofetil	Antitumor	It Inhibits IMDH	20
8	Tacrolimus	Antirejection	It Diminishes lymphocyte inhibition	23

Table: - 2 Immunoadjuvant drug and plant-derived bioactive immunoadjuvant.

S.NO	DRUG	USES	MECHANISM OF ACTION	REF
1	Levamisole (Ergamisol)	5-Fluorouracil adjuvant therapy following surgical removal improves outcomes in patients with Duke's stage C colon cancer.	By Inducing B & T lymphocytes, Monocytes & macrophages	24
2	Plant-derived bioactive Pectic arabinogalactan (polysaccharide)	Combining 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) enhances thymus gland immune response.	Polysaccharides stimulate murine thymus lymphocyte proliferation by modulating intracellular calcium ion levels.	25

Table: - 3 Immunostimulant drug and plant-derived bioactive immunostimulant.

S.NO	DRUG	USES	MECHANISM OF ACTION	REF
1	(R)-Thalidomide	Used to treat multiple myeloma, treat rheumatoid arthritis & angiogenesis	Inhibit myeloma proliferation that may decrease antibody production	26
2	Immunocyanin (hemocyanin)	Used to treat urinary bladder cancer	It supplies oxygen to the affected area	26
3	Bestatin	Used as Antitumor activity and shows more antitumor activity of bleomycin & adriamycin	By binding cell surfaces, it enhances lymphocyte and macrophage function, boosting adaptive immune responses.	26
4	Plant bioactive Curcumin (polyphenol)	Exhibits Antiproliferative, anticancer & antiangiogenic activity	Helps to Increase white blood cells count	27
5	Genistein (phytoestrogen)	Helps to treat diabetes	Produce NO and PGE2, rise insulin resistance	22

Table: - 4 Low and high molecular weight natural products used as an immunomodulator.

S.NO	DRUG	EXAMPLES	REF
1	Low molecular weight compounds Alkaloid	Cocaine, vincristine	28
2	Terpenoids	Sesquiterpene lactones, diterpenes & triterpenes	28
3	Phenolics	Flavonoids, coumarins & quinones	28
4	High molecular weight compounds Lectins	Concanavalin A	28
5	Polysaccharides	Glucans, lentinans, & arabinogalactans	28

Immunomodulatory Plants: -

Phytochemicals exhibiting immunomodulatory properties include essential oils, steroids, polyphenols, flavonoids, diterpenoids, alkaloids, and phytoestrogens [29]. Research has identified approximately 150 medicinal plants possessing immunomodulatory activity. These plants, categorized by family, demonstrate varying mechanisms of action and bioactive compounds. A comprehensive tabulation of plant parts, responsible phytochemicals, and mechanisms of action is available. Notably, a pie chart constructed from these references illustrates the distribution of immunomodulatory plants across different families.

TABLE: - 5. Plant derived immunomodulatory agents [30-37]

S.NO	PLANT SOURCE	PARTS USED	CHEMICAL CONSTITUENT	MECHANISM OF ACTION
1	Allium sativum	Bulb	Allicin	Decreases the leukocyte inflammatory cytokine production
2	Aloe vera(L)	Leaves	Anthraquinone glycoside	Rise the phagocytosis & stimulating the production of superoxide
3	Asparagus racemosus	Roots	Saponins, sitosterol	Stimulates the production of leukocytosis.
4	Azadirachta indica A.	Leaves	Azadirachtin	Enhances IgM and IgG antibody production while inhibiting nitric oxide synthesis and neutrophil degranulation.

5	<i>Argyrea speciosa</i> (L.f)	Roots & seeds	Glycosides	Increases the production of circulation antibody & Increase in DTH reaction
6	<i>Boerhaavia diffusa</i> L.	Roots	Alkaloids	Suppresses human natural killer cell cytotoxicity and inhibits NO and IL-2 production in vitro.
7	<i>Bidens Pilosa</i> L.	Whole plants	Flavonoids, Linolic acid, polyacetylenes	Stimulates the cytokine production and WBC populations
8	<i>Boswellia serrate</i> Roxb.	Bark	Boswellia acids, Essential oils	Prevent the passive paw anaphylaxis reactions and mast cell protections
9	<i>Calendula officinalis</i> L.	Leaves& flowers	Fatty acids, proteins, Polysaccharides	Prohibit cancer cell growth & proliferation.
10	<i>Citrus nobilis</i>	Fruits& leaves	Nobiletin	Reduces PHA-stimulated mononuclear cell growth and staphylococcal protein-induced activation.
11	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> (L).	Leaves	Epigallocatechin-3 gallate	Boosts the neopterin
12	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L).	Leaves	Asiaticoside, Madecassoside	It elevates the phagocytic index; total WBC count & suppress human peripheral blood mononuclear cell
13	<i>Chelidonium majus</i> L.	Aerial parts	Chelerythrine	It exhibits anti-tumor immunostimulatory effect
14	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Rhizome	Curcumin	Exerts the immunomodulation through inhibition of proliferation induced by PMA & Anti-CD28 antibody.
15	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> (L).	Whole plant	Alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids	Increases NO synthesis, enhancing resistance to <i>Leishmania donovani</i> .
16	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L).	Whole plants	Phenolic acids, flavonoids, triterpenoids	Stimulates phagocytic activity, enhances non-specific immunity and boosts lysosomal function in humoral responses.
17	<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> (L).	Whole plants	Alkaloids, oleic & linoleic acid.	Suppress the level of NOS Exert adaptogenic property

18	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Herb	Gallic acid, quercitol	Exhibits the phagocytic activity.
19	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Whole plant	Alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins.	Boosts human neutrophil phagocytic activity in vitro.
20	<i>Ficus carica</i>	Leaf	Phenolic compounds, volatile oils, phytosterols.	Exhibits cellular immune & humoral antibody reaction
21	<i>Fallopia japonica</i> .	Rhizome	Resveratrol	Suppresses MPO, MPEGs-1, iNOS and COX-2, restoring basal cellular activity.
22	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> L.	Bark & Roots	Glycyrrhizin, isoflavones, Glycyrrhetic acid	Strengthens immune & anti-oxidant enzyme activities
23	<i>Gelsemium elegans</i>	Leaves & Stems	Gelselegine, Koumine	Prohibit T- lymphocyte proliferation
24	<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i>	Whole plant	Flavonoids, polysaccharides, triterpenes	Proliferation of T- lymphocytes
25	<i>Hyptis suaveolnes</i>	Leaf, flower	Lupeol, sitosterol	Exhibits humoral immunity reactions.
26	<i>Hippophae rhamnoides</i> L.	Leaves & Fruits	Isorhamnetic, pectin, flavonoids	Suppresses chromium-induced oxidative stress and apoptosis, while enhancing IL-2 and IFN production.
27	<i>Hydrastis canadensis</i> L.	Roots	Alkaloids, berberine	Prohibit the T- helper type-II cytokine profile
28	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	Leaves	Flavonoids, lignans	Boosts the antibody titers, lymphocyte & macrophages
29	<i>Luffa cylindrica</i>	Seeds & leaves	Echinocystic acid	Increases phagocytic index of macrophages, linking cell-mediated & humoral immune defenses.
30	<i>Lycoris radiate</i>	Flowers	Lycorine	Prohibits iNOS & COX-2 functions.
31	<i>Lonicera japonica</i>	Leaves	Luteolin	Diminishes inflammatory response by decreasing COX-2, ICAM-1 and cytokine production.

32	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Stem bark	Alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins	Boosts antibody response, augmenting IgG1 and IgG2b levels and strengthening DTH.
33	<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> L.	Flowers	Flavonoids, essential oils	Stimulates peripheral blood immune cells and enhances effector cell responsiveness to helper signals.
34	<i>Mollugo verticillate</i> L.	Leaves	Flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins.	Blocks the production of NO
35	<i>Moringa citrifolia</i> L.	Fruits	Alkaloids, organic acids	Provoke the release of IL-10, 12 & IFN.
36	<i>Nigella sativa</i>		Thymoquinone	Blocks LPS-stimulated fibroblast growth and inhibits H ₂ O ₂ -generated 4-hydroxynonenal formation.
37	<i>Nyctanthes arbortristis</i>	Leaf	Iridoid glucosides	It exhibits Humoral immunity & DTH
38	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn	Rhizome & seed	Flavonoid, Alkaloids	Decreases NO production while stabilizing mast cells against degranulation.
39	<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	Leaves	Alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins	Inhibits the production of hemagglutination antibodies, diminishes DTH responses & phagocytic index.
40	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Entire plant	Essential oils such as eugenol, carvacrol, derivatives of ursolic acid.	Increases the release of RBC, WBC & hemoglobin.
41	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i>	Aerial parts	Flavonoids, tannins, saponins	Suppresses antigen-stimulated histamine release from mast cells, leukocyte migration and footpad swelling.
42	<i>Piper longum</i>	Fruits	Alkaloids	Enhance the total WBC count & bone marrow cellularity, increases the production of total antibody.
43	<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i>	Leaf	Alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins	Exhibits the cell-mediated & humoral elements
44	<i>Plantago asiatica</i>	Seed	Phenolic compounds, Flavonoids.	Exhibits increased MHC class II and costimulatory molecule expression, enhancing IFN- γ release.
45	<i>Punica granatum</i> L.	Fruits	Punicalagin, tannins, ellagic acid.	Blocks the migration of leucocytes.
46	<i>Premna tomentosa</i> Willd	Stem bark	Limonene, Flavonoids & phenolics.	Prohibits the lymphocyte proliferation, suppress the antioxidant levels

47	Rhinacanthus nasutus L.	Whole plant	Rhincanthin-C.	Enhancing the release of IL-II.
48	Salacia chinensis	Roots	Flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, carbohydrates	Displays significant HA antibody levels & DTH reactions.
49	Silybum marianum	Flowers	Flavonoids	Exhibits the migration of Macrophage cells
50	Syzygium cumini	Seeds	Alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, phytosterols	Assesses immune function using carbon clearance & hemagglutination inhibition and DTH.
51	Salicornia herbacea	Herb	Polysaccharides	Demonstrates enhanced phagocytic activity on opsonized.
52	Trapa bispinosa	Fruits	Flavonoids, proteins, carbohydrates	It shows Neutrophils & hemagglutination titer
53	Tinospora cordifolia	Whole plant	Alkaloids	Enhance the total WBC count & bone marrow cellularity, increases the production of total antibody.
54	Tramarindus indica L.	Fruits	Phenolic compounds, Flavonoids, vitamin-C	Suppress PMA-induced neutrophil activation and elastase release.
55	Terminalia chebula Retz.	Fruits	Flavonoids, tannins, sterols.	Stimulates the HA titer and DTH response.
56	Urtica dioica L.	Aerial parts	Alkaloids, flavonoids.	Decreases TNF- α and inflammatory cytokines by blocking transcriptional regulation.
57	Uncaria rhynchophylla	Leaves	Rhynchophylline	Suppresses the production of pro-inflammatory mediators, including TNF- α , NO, PGE2 and MCP-1.
58	Withania somniferaL.	Roots	Alkaloids, steroidal lactones.	Stimulates total WBC count & bone marrow cellularity. Shows phagocytic activity on macrophages cell.

Curcuma longa: -

Curcuma longa, a perennial herb widely distributed all over in India. Curcumin is a natural diarylheptanoid compound found in the rhizome of Curcuma longa and related species. Curcumin, an extensively studied bioactive compound, exhibits a broad spectrum of biological activities, including cancer prevention, oxidative stress reduction, and inhibition of angiogenesis and cell proliferation. Moreover, its

immunomodulatory properties have been widely explored, highlighting curcumin's potential to modulate the immune system. The biochemical makeup of turmeric is characterized by a rich blend of macronutrients, minerals, and volatile/non-volatile oils. The curcuminoid fraction, comprising curcumin (60-70%), desmethoxycurcumin (20-27%), bisdemethoxycurcumin (10-15%), is supplemented by trace amounts of dihydro curcumin and

cyclocurcumin. Furthermore, turmeric's phytochemical diversity extends to sesquiterpenes, diterpenes, triterpenoids, and turmerones [38]. Curcumin demonstrates anti-inflammatory activity by inhibiting key molecular targets, including NO production, COX-2, NK- κ B, iNOS, and lipoxygenase, in NK cells and macrophages activated by IFN- γ or TNF- α . Numerous evidences suggest that curcumin has both proliferation and activation of T cells. It was reported that curcumin inhibits the proliferation induced by PMA and anti-CD28 antibody. A thorough review [39] of 116 pre-clinical and clinical trials, conducted across multiple research centers, has elucidated the far-reaching benefits of curcumin, highlighting its potential therapeutic utility. Analysis of the 116 studies reveals a strong focus on curcumin's anti-inflammatory properties, with 99 studies exploring its potential in alleviating various conditions. Cancer (including multiple types), rheumatoid arthritis, and inflammatory bowel diseases (IBD) are among the primary areas of investigation. As research continues, upcoming clinical trials will concentrate on curcumin's effects on cancer, cognitive function, and inflammatory disorders. Furthermore, curcumin's potential as a complementary therapeutic agent or dietary supplement to conventional treatments will remain a key area of exploration. Still, from the available literature, a conclusion can be drawn that curcumin exhibits good safety profile; it is nontoxic and well tolerated

Andrographis paniculata: -

Andrographis paniculata traditionally called as King of Bitters, Kalmegh, is a medicinal plant belongs to *Acanthaceae* family. It is widely distributed through Southeast Asia, China, West Indies, America, Thailand, Malaysia, and Japan. It has bitter taste and colourless appearance. *A. paniculata* is used in the world as ayurvedic and homeopathic medicine, consisting mainly flavonoids (flavone), polyphenols, terpenoids (diterpene, lactones, Ent-labdane), xanthenes, nocordioides. Research over the past few decades has revealed that andrographolides and their derivatives possess multifaceted immunomodulatory properties, enhancing immune function through two primary mechanisms: (1) antigen-specific immunity, where they stimulate antibody production to combat bacterial infections, and (2) non-specific immunity, activating macrophages to recognize and eliminate pathogens. Additionally, these compounds have exhibited a broad spectrum of biological activities, including antiviral, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-platelet, antidiabetic, antitumor, antimicrobial, and hepatoprotective effects, showcasing their potential as therapeutic agents [40]. Andrographolide, the primary bioactive compound in *Andrographis paniculata*, is predominantly found in the plant's leaves.

Chemically classified as 3- α , 14, 15, 18-tetrahydroxy-5- β , 9- β H, 10- α -labda-8, 12-dien-16-oic acid gamma-lactone, andrographolide has demonstrated potent anti-inflammatory properties in laboratory settings. Specifically, studies have shown that andrographolide significantly reduces the production of pro-inflammatory mediators, including IL-12, TNF- α , NO, PGE2, COX-2, and iNOS, in microglia and macrophages. Furthermore, it inhibits LPS-induced iNOS and COX-2 expression in RAW264.7 murine macrophage cell lines, highlighting its potential therapeutic role in modulating immune responses. Andrographolide boosts the immune system by increasing lymphocyte growth and IL-2 production. However, it also regulates overactive immune responses by reducing IL-2 production in certain cells. Furthermore, andrographolide reduces inflammation by blocking the production of harmful chemicals like TNF- α and IL-12.

Moringa oleifera: -

Moringa oleifera has been used in folk remedies by Polynesians for over 2000 years and it has a wide range of therapeutic activities such as antiviral, antibacterial, antifungal, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, & immune enhancing effect. The active constituents of *moringa oleifera* includes n-hexadecenoic acid, tetra decanoic acid, cis-vaccenic acid, octadecanoic acid, vitamin E, gamma sitosterol, squalane, 2,6-dihydroxy benzoic acid, quinic acid, hexadecanal, phytol, panthonin, vanillin, moringine, moringinine. Research on *Moringa oleifera*'s methanolic extract revealed optimal immune response stimulation at low doses (250 mg/kg), surpassing that of high doses (750 mg/kg). Neutrophil adhesion assays demonstrated the extract's capacity to activate neutrophils, directing them to inflammation sites. Notably, both low and high doses of the methanolic extract mitigated cyclophosphamide-induced neutropenia, suggesting a protective effect on the hematopoietic system, which is responsible for blood cell production. *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract exhibits robust antioxidant activity, scavenging free radicals and preventing oxidative stress due to its rich polyphenol content. Furthermore, *M. oleifera* selectively suppresses the expression of inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) and cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), thereby inhibiting the release of nitric oxide, tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), prostaglandin E2 (PGE-2), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β) in lipopolysaccharide-stimulated RAW264.7 cells. Notably, isothiocyanates isolated from *M. oleifera* demonstrate potent anti-cancer properties [41]. *M. oleifera* is given as a nutraceutical because of its safety to treat various chronic problems. After ingestion of *moringa oleifera*

extract show reduced blood glucose levels within 3 hours.

Tinospora cordifolia:-

Tinospora cordifolia traditionally known as Guduchi in Sanskrit, commonly called as moonseed, giloy which is a biologically, abundant, wide, deciduous, climbing shrub with greenish, typical yellow flowers belongs to the family Menispermaceae. T. cordifolia mainly found in tropical Indian-subcontinent, China. The plant shows wide range of therapeutic properties ranging from basic tonic, anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritic, anti-malarial, aphrodisiac, anti-allergic, anti-diabetic, anti-hepatotoxic, wound healing effect and anti-pyretic properties are shown and has relatively low toxicity[42]. The active phytochemical constituents of T. cordifolia includes clerodane Furano diterpene glycoside, cordioside, syringin, Cordifolioside A, Cordifolioside B, cordiol. The ethyl acetate extract of Tinospora cordifolia exhibits immunomodulatory effects, including the proliferation of stem cells, enhancement of white blood cells (WBCs), and increased antibody-producing cells. Furthermore, the leaf extract demonstrates broad-spectrum antibacterial activity against pathogens such as E. coli, Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus pyogenes, Bacillus subtilis, and Proteus vulgaris. Notably, T. cordifolia surpasses cyclophosphamide in reducing tumor growth [43]. By activating B and T cells, it enhances humoral and cell-mediated immunity, compensating for compromised innate immunity. Ultimately, T. cordifolia fortifies the overall immune system, promoting host defense and well-being.

Screening methods for immunomodulation: - [45]

In vitro methods	In vivo methods
Inhibition of histamine release from mast cells	Anti anaphylactic activity (Schultz-Dale reaction)
Mitogen induced lymphocyte proliferation	Porcine cardiac myosin-induced autoimmune myocarditis in rats
Inhibition of T-cell proliferation	Acute systemic anaphylaxis in rats
Chemiluminescence in macrophages	Arthus-type immediate hypersensitivity
Plaque-forming colony test	Delayed type hypersensitivity
MTT assay	Passive cutaneous anaphylaxis
Inducible nitric oxide synthase activity	Prevention of experimental induced myasthenia gravis in rats
Neutrophil adhesion test	Adjuvant arthritis in rats
Hemagglutination antibody titer	Collagen type 2 induced arthritis in rats

Future perspectives: -

For centuries, plant-based medicines and traditional remedies have inspired the development of therapeutic agents. Herbal and botanical products offer viable alternatives to conventional chemotherapy. Currently, researchers are focused on plant-derived therapeutics, studying specific plant biochemicals as lead molecules targeting disease-related mechanisms. Numerous plant complexes with immunomodulatory properties have been identified, but a multidisciplinary approach is necessary to isolate active constituents from medicinal plants and elucidate their effects using modern techniques. Two strategies can be employed for developing drugs from medicinal plants: the phytochemical approach, which involves identifying and developing pure phytochemicals as drugs (though costly and time-consuming), and the phototherapeutic approach, which utilizes standardized crude drug preparations as drugs with modern safety and efficacy standards. The latter approach is particularly suitable for Indian therapeutic plants [44].

Screening methods for immunomodulatory property: -

To evaluate the efficacy and safety of plant-derived bioactive compounds, researchers employ in vitro (laboratory-based) and in vivo (animal-based) models. These models assess the immunomodulatory properties of isolated and extracted plant constituents, demonstrating their potential bioactivities. A comprehensive overview of in vitro and in vivo models is provided, summarizing their applications in evaluating immunomodulatory activity.

CONCLUSION:

The immune system is vital for host survival, which offers protection through its diverse immune cells, proteins, and cell signalling pathways. These complex networks effectively eliminate various pathogens. However, the immune system's imperfections can lead to dysfunctional responses triggered by external or internal factors, resulting in autoimmunity, hypersensitivity, and cancer. The global health burden is increasingly affected by autoimmune diseases, with neurological diseases rising by 3.7% and endocrinal, gastrointestinal, and rheumatic diseases by 6% annually. Furthermore, cancer poses a significant threat, with the World Health Organization predicting 15 million new cases yearly by 2020. Notably, 2018 saw an estimated 18.1 million cancer cases, exceeding previous predictions by 3 million. Immunomodulatory agents are therapeutic compounds that modify the immune system's response, either enhancing immunostimulants, immunosuppressants or immunomodulators. These drugs are primarily used to treat autoimmune diseases, allergies, AIDS, cancer, and select viral infections. This review focuses on plant-derived immunomodulators, detailing their phytochemical composition and mechanisms of action. By exploring traditional medicine, this review aims to identify natural lead compounds for drug development and validate their efficacy. Various plants with potential immunomodulatory properties are discussed, alongside others exhibiting similar activities, to uncover natural immunomodulators. Therefore, this review aims to provide researchers with a comprehensive understanding of natural immunostimulants, while also facilitating the exploration and utilization of traditional medicines for the discovery and development of novel drugs.

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